

THE REACTIVITY OF DIETHYL 2 : 4-DINITROPHENYLMALONATE

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Diethyl 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl-*n*-propylmalonate has been prepared, an improved method for its preparation has been worked out and a tentative explanation for the remarkable stability and colour of its sodium derivative has been put forward.

It is well known that the halogen atom in 1-halogenated 2 : 4-dinitrobenzenes is reactive and yields condensation products with the sodium derivatives of acetoacetic and malonic esters. Considerable work has been done on this subject (Richter, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2470 ; Reissert and Heller, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4364 ; Borsche, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 601 ; Dey and Doraiswami, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 309). None of the above workers, except Borsche, described any attempt to prepare substitution derivatives of 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl-acetoacetic and -malonic esters. Both these compounds readily yield their sodium derivatives but according to Borsche the sodium derivative of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylacetoacetic ester fails to react either with ethyl iodide or benzyl chloride, reacting, however, with a second molecule of bromo-2 : 4-dinitrobenzene to yield 2 : 4 : 2' : 4' tetranitrodiphenylacetoacetic ester (Borsche, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1311). He also failed to effect this condensation starting from α -alkyl acetoacetic esters and allowing their sodium derivatives to react with 1-bromo-2 : 4-dinitrobenzene. Borsche concluded therefore that the hydrogen atom in the acetoacetic ester grouping of 2 : 4-dinitrophenylacetoacetic ester did not react with alkyl halides

As there is no mention in literature of any attempt, either by the above mentioned or other authors, to condense the sodium derivative of diethyl 2 : 4-dinitrophenylmalonate with any alkyl halide and as the present authors required such compounds as intermediates in connection with other work, they tried the condensation of the above mentioned compound with propyl bromide as a test case. The condensation has been successfully effected both ways, that is, both by condensing sodio-propyl malonic ester with 1-chloro-2 : 4-dinitrobenzene and by condensing the sodium derivative of diethyl 2 : 4-dinitrophenylmalonate with propyl bromide, the solvents used being dry ether-benzene mixture in the first case (yield 54% of theory) and absolute ethyl alcohol in the second (yield 23% of theory). The yields obtained in the second stage of condensation are thus considerably less than those obtained in the first stage of condensation of the monosodio malonic ester with 1-chloro-2 : 4-dinitrobenzene (yield 90% of theory). It is thus obvious that the presence of 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl-group in the 2 : 4-dinitrophenylmalonic and -acetoacetic esters leads to the formation at the second stage of substitution, of stable sodium derivatives which undergo further condensation with alkyl halides only with reluctance in the case of malonic ester derivatives and not at all in the case of acetoacetic ester derivatives as found earlier by Borsche (*loc. cit.*).

The sodium derivative of diethyl 2 : 4-dinitrophenylmalonate is characterised by remarkable stability. It is a crimson-red, beautifully crystalline solid which is quite unlike other gelatinous sodio derivatives and decomposes only on heating above

The reaction has been shown to be bimolecular by carrying out experiments with different initial concentrations of the reactants in equimolecular proportions. The time required for 25% change varied inversely to the initial concentration within experimental errors as required for a reaction of the second order. Velocity constants were calculated by the usual equation for a reaction of the second order,

$$k = \frac{x}{2a(a-x)t}$$

where k = the velocity constant ; a = initial concentration of each reactant ; x = change in concentration ; t = time.

The concentrations are all expressed in g. mols./litre and the time in hours. The following table gives the results of a typical experiment.

TABLE I

Reaction between methyl benzoate and aniline at 100° in nitrobenzene.

Aniline = 0.1 g. mol /litre ; methyl benzoate = 0.1 g. mol./litre.

Time.	x .	$a-x$.	$10k$.	Time.	x .	$a-x$.	$10k$.
0 hr.	0.00000	0.09300		5 hr	0.02790	0.06510	7.010
1	0.00620	0.08680	7.010	8	0.03472	0.05828	7.440
2	0.01240	0.08060	7.692	10	0.03840	0.05460	7.050
3	0.01474	0.07826	7.316	20	0.05398	0.03902	7.010
4	0.02148	0.07152	7.050	30	0.06225	0.03075	7.012
						Mean	7.22

The unsubstituted ester was found to behave abnormally and hence the velocity constants of the reaction between methyl benzoate and aniline were redetermined several times using different samples of aniline. The same value for velocity constants was obtained in each case.

The velocity constants were used to calculate the activation energy E and the probability factor, P by using the equation,

$$k = PZe^{-E/RT}$$

The values of E , thus obtained graphically, were checked by the method of least squares (cf. Hartmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1714). The probability factor P was determined in the same way. Z was assumed to be 2.8×10^{11} (cf. Hinshelwood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1357).

The following table gives the values of the velocity constants $10k$, the activation energies and the probability factors. The activation energies are given to the nearest 100 calories. The values actually obtained by calculation are given in brackets. In Fig. 1. $\log k$ has been plotted against $1/T$ for the reaction between aniline and methyl benzoate as a typical case.

Fig. 1.

TABLE II

Reaction between esters of substituted benzoic acids and aniline in nitrobenzene as solvent.

Temp.	10k.	E.	$P \times 10^4$.	10k.	E.	$P \times 10^4$.
	(1) Methyl benzoate.			(2) Methyl o-nitrobenzoate.		
80°	4.90			13.46		
100	7.22			18.21		
115	10.90			22.92	4200	
125	13.99	6200		28.23	(4210)	7.8
145	19.06	(6120)	7.8			
	(3) Methyl m-nitrobenzoate.			(4) Methyl p-nitrobenzoate.		
80°	16.25			15.82		
100	22.34			26.91		
115	28.16	2800		33.14	3800	
125	32.39	(3780)	15.6	37.16	(3770)	8.1
	(5) Methyl o-bromobenzoate.			(6) Methyl m-bromobenzoate.		
80°	11.58			13.81		
100	17.23			18.03		
125	27.52	4600		27.71	4600	
145	34.25	(4560)	3.7	38.65	(4540)	3.9
	(7) Methyl p-bromobenzoate.			(8) Methyl o-chlorobenzoate.		
80°	16.07			10.72		
100	22.26			14.79		
125	32.78	4300		21.88	4500	
145	39.41	(4280)	9.0	28.84	(4510)	8.2
	(9) Methyl m-chlorobenzoate.			(10) Methyl p-chlorobenzoate.		
80°	11.75			15.85		
100	16.60			21.88		
125	25.70	4500		30.20	4200	
145	35.83	(4480)	3.6	36.31	(4170)	3.8

120°. The stability and the colour of this compound might be explained as probably due to resonance, the structures mainly contributing to the mesomeric form possibly being (I) and (II).

The increased stability of this sodium compound would also explain its reduced reactivity and the consequent low yields obtained in its condensation with propyl bromide.

The present authors have also worked out a greatly improved method of preparing diethyl 2:4-dinitrophenylmalonate in 90% yield. This ester was first prepared by Richter (*loc. cit.*) by refluxing an equimolecular mixture of 1-bromo-2:4-dinitrobenzene and malonic ester with sodium ethoxide in absolute alcohol. The product obtained was reported to be an oil which Richter could crystallise only with great difficulty and by a tedious process. Dey and Doraiswami (*loc. cit.*) also claim to have prepared it subsequently by the same method. It is found by the present authors that the best results could be obtained by bringing about the condensation in dry ether using twice the molecular quantities of sodium and malonic ester. The sodium compound separated out as a crimson-red, crystalline solid on rubbing up the pasty reaction mass with a little ice-cold water. It was then decomposed by cold dilute nitric acid to give diethyl 2:4-dinitrophenylmalonate.

Attempts to hydrolyse diethyl 2:4-dinitrophenyl-*n*-propylmalonate have not yet succeeded. Among the hydrolytic agents tried by the present authors are aqueous and alcoholic sodium hydroxide, dilute hydrochloric acid, dilute sulphuric acid, concentrated hydrochloric acid and a mixture of glacial acetic and concentrated sulphuric acids. This obviously seems to be a case of steric hindrance in keeping with the observation of Hjelt (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 110, 1864) that disubstituted malonic esters are hydrolysed only with great difficulty where the substituents are large in size.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethyl 2:4-Dinitrophenylmalonate.—In a three-necked round bottom flask, fitted with an efficient mercury-sealed mechanical stirrer, a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, the mono-sodium derivative of diethyl malonate was prepared from 2.3 g. of sodium, 30 c.c. dry ether, and 16g. of malonic ester. The flask was immersed in ice-cold water and a solution of 10.2 g. (0.05 mol.) of 1-chloro-2:4-dinitrobenzene in 100 c.c. of absolute ether was

added gradually and with constant stirring during the course of 2 hours. The ice-water was then removed and the contents refluxed for 9 hours. The ether was then decanted after cooling, the excess of malonic ester and any unreacted 1-chloro-2:4 dinitrobenzene coming over with the ether. Ice-cold water (60 c.c.) was then added to the brown pasty reaction mass left in the flask. A bright red crystalline precipitate (sodio-derivative of diethyl 2:4-dinitrophenylmalonate) was thus obtained and was filtered at the pump. The ethereal portion was extracted repeatedly with cold 3% sodium hydroxide till no more colour came in the alkali extract. The crystalline red precipitate was suspended in the alkali extract in a beaker and crushed ice was added to it. Dilute nitric acid was then added drop by drop till the red colour was completely discharged. 2:4-Dinitrophenylmalonic ester separated as a pale yellow crystalline precipitate which gave colourless plates on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, m.p. 51° , yield 14.5 g. (90%). (Found: N, 8.32. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.59 per cent).

The red sodio-derivative obtained above is remarkably stable towards air and water. It decomposes between 120° and 125° on heating in a capillary. (Found: N, 7.71. $C_{13}H_{13}O_4N_2Na$ requires N, 8.05 per cent).

Diethyl 2:4-Dinitrophenyl-n-propylmalonate.—Diethyl propylmalonate (5 g., 0.025 mole), prepared as usual, was added drop by drop to 0.58 g. (0.025 mole) of sodium ribbon suspended in a mixture of 20 c.c. dry ether and 20 c.c. dry benzene cooled in water. After the addition was complete the mixture was refluxed for 10 minutes and the flask was then cooled in ice-water. 2:4-Dinitrochlorobenzene (0.025 mole, 5 g.) dissolved in 50 c.c. of absolute ether was then slowly added during the course of 2 hours. The mixture was finally refluxed for 7 hours and the ether and benzene then distilled off. The residue was treated with 1% cold hydrochloric and the acid decanted off from the oil which had separated. After washing the oil free of acid with water it was dissolved in 100 c.c. of cold alcohol and left over for slow evaporation. After about 3 weeks the mass became crystalline. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol it gave colourless needles, m. p. 72° , yield 5 g. (54% of theory). (Found: N, 7.99. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.61 per cent).

Diethyl 2:4-Dinitrophenyl-n-propylmalonate from Propyl Bromide and Diethyl Sodio-2:4-dinitrophenylmalonate.—The sodium derivative of 2:4-dinitrophenylmalonic ester (3.5g., previously washed with ether and dried in vacuum) was dissolved in 10 c.c. of absolute alcohol and refluxed for 10 hours with freshly distilled propyl bromide (1.3 g.). The alcohol was then distilled off and the residue acidified with cold 1% hydrochloric acid, the rest of the treatment being as above, m.p. 73° (mixed melting point with a specimen of this ester prepared by the first method), yield 0.85 g. (20% of theory). (Found: N, 7.99. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 7.61 per cent.).

TABLE II (contd.)

Temp.	10k.	E.	$P \times 10^7$	10k	E.	$p \times 10^7$.
	(11) Methyl <i>o</i> -methoxybenzoate.			(12) Methyl <i>m</i> -methoxybenzoate.		
100°	11.37			13.98		
115	14.79			17.71		
125	18.79	5000		20.34	4800	
145	25.73	(4960)	8.1	27.43	(4830)	3.2
	(13) Methyl <i>p</i> -methoxybenzoate.			(14) Methyl <i>o</i> -hydroxybenzoate.		
100°	15.26			11.23		
115	17.93			14.46		
125	24.53	4300		17.39	5400	1.0
145	32.13	(4270)	5.9	23.95	(5370)	
	(15) Methyl <i>m</i> -hydroxybenzoate.			(16) Methyl <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoate.		
100°	12.24			14.43		
115	16.37			18.21		
125	20.93	5000		22.36	5600	
145	29.57	(4990)	1.9	29.50	(4960)	1.6
	(17) Methyl <i>o</i> -toluate.			(18) Methyl <i>m</i> -toluate		
80°	5.28			7.51		
100	7.94			11.18		
115	12.51	4800		14.12	4700	
125	14.10	(4840)	5.2	16.63	(4720)	5.3
	(19) Methyl <i>p</i> -toluate.					
80°	6.63					
100	11.80					
115	15.16	4600				
125	17.40	(4630)	4.9			

Probability Factor, 'P'.—Table III gives the values of P and E of the reactions between methyl esters of substituted benzoic acid and aniline in nitrobenzene.

TABLE III

Substituent.	<i>Ortho.</i>		<i>Meso.</i>		<i>Para.</i>	
	$P \times 10^7$.	E .	$P \times 10^7$.	E .	$P \times 10^7$.	E .
Nitro	7.8	4200	15.5	3800	8.1	3800
Bromo	3.7	4600	4.0	4500	9.0	4300
Chloro	5.2	4500	3.6	4500	8.8	4300
Methoxy	8.1	5000	3.2	4800	5.9	4300
Hydroxy	1.0	5400	1.9	5000	1.8	5000
Methyl	5.2	4800	5.3	4700	4.9	4600
Methyl benzoate	7.3	6200	—	—	—	—

It will be observed from the above table, that the probability factor, P is of the order of 10^{-7} and does not vary much, the maximum variation being 1:25 except in case of methyl *m*-nitrobenzoate and hydroxybenzoates. This variation might be more apparent than real, because the accuracy with

which P has been determined is comparatively much small in this series of experiments than is usual, most of the experiments having been carried out between the range of 80° and 145° . Generally, reaction velocities are studied at about 25° and the temperature can be kept constant within $\pm 0.01^\circ$ at such temperatures. At the high temperatures, as used in these experiments, the variation is as large as 0.1° . Therefore, errors in the measurements in the present work must be larger than usual. The variation of P therefore can be neglected and assumed to be constant.

This conclusion is further justified by a study of the velocity constant and activation energy. In Fig. 2 $\log k$ has been plotted against E , the activation energy. It will be found that the points lie near the straight line with the theoretical slope $-2.303 RT$.

Fig. 2

The maximum deviation in E from the line does not amount to more than 200 calories except in m -nitro and o -, m - and p -hydroxy esters. Therefore, the conclusion that the probability factor, P is constant within reasonable limits and the effect of the substituents is mainly on the activation energy is justified.

Probable Mechanism of the Reaction

The reaction of a base with an ester might be considered to be very similar to the alkaline hydrolysis of an ester. The justification for this assumption can only be given if the mechanism of this reaction is shown to be of the same type as alkaline hydrolysis of esters.

J. Chem. Soc., 1938, 1801; Tommila, *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicae Ser.*, 1941, A, 57, No. 13, 3) the order in all the three series of substituents is
 $\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl}$ and $\text{Br} > \text{OCH}_3 > \text{H} > \text{CH}_3$

The order of the effect of substituents is identical in the present work as well as in the alkaline hydrolysis of esters up to OCH_3 group. However, the effect of methyl group in the alkaline hydrolysis of esters is to retard the reaction, while in our case the velocity is increased. This anomaly of the position of the unsubstituted ester in the two series of reactions cannot be explained at this stage.

The effect of individual substituent in different positions follows the order: p -> m -> o - in our case, while in alkaline hydrolysis of esters, the order, with the exception of NO_2 group, is m -> p -> o - Thus the order of effect due to the position of the substituent is different in alkaline hydrolysis of esters from the effect of substituents in the present work. The values of constants for alkaline hydrolysis of esters for OCH_3 group in *ortho* and *para* positions and that of OH in o -, m -, and p - positions are not known.

Likewise, the effect of substituents in benzoyl chloride in the benzylation of anilines (Hinshelwood and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1079) follows the same order as in the alkaline hydrolysis of esters, and the reaction studied here, e.g. $\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > \text{H} > \text{CH}_3$.

The results now may be discussed in the light of polarity of substituents. The mechanism proposed for the reaction shows that it is a class 'B' reaction. In class B reactions the activation energy, E is decreased and the reaction velocity increased by the presence of an electron attracting substituent, (NO_2 , Cl , Br , OCH_3 , etc.), while the presence of an electron repelling substituent (CH_3) should decrease the reaction velocity. The effect of electron attracting groups is of the right order in the present reaction; the effect of the electron repelling group (to retard the reaction) is, however, not observed in the present case as noted above and is abnormal.

Velocity constants of esterification of benzoic acids with *cyclohexanol* have been determined by Hartman and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1714). The results show that with the exception of *m*-toluic and *p*-methoxybenzoic acids the introduction of any substituent in the *m*- and *p*-positions in the benzoic acid molecule decreases the activation energy, E and P as well. In the case of *m*-toluic acid, the velocity constant is greater than benzoic acid, while in *p*-toluic acid it is slightly lower. Excluding *o*-substituents and *m*-methoxy and *m*-toluic acid, it is found that all the substituents increase the reaction velocity as compared with the unsubstituted benzoic acid, irrespective of the polarity of the substituents. This is quite analogous to the present case, where the methyl substituted benzoic esters have enhanced the rates. This similarity might be due to the second reactant being a cyclic derivative (*cyclohexanol* in their case and *aniline* in the present case).

Previous workers (*cf.* Evans, Morgan and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935; 1174) have observed that a relationship between velocity constants and dipole moments of the corresponding substituted benzenes is given by the relation,

$$\log k/Z = \log k_0/Z_0 \pm x(\mu + \alpha\mu^2)$$

where $Z = N^2\sigma ab^2(8\pi RT/M)^{1/2}$ σab being the mean diameter and $\frac{1}{M} = \frac{1}{m_a} + \frac{1}{m_b}$, m_a and m_b being the respective molecular weights.

For comparative purposes $\log k/Z$ may be taken as $\log(k\sqrt{M})$ as $N^2\sigma ab^2(8\pi RT)^{1/2}$ will be nearly constant. (*cf.* Hinshelwood and Williams, *loc. cit.*)

In an isotypical series of reaction $\log k_0/Z_0$ is constant and therefore if $\log k/Z$ is plotted against dipole moment of substituted benzenes, a curve should be obtained. In the present work $\log k/Z$ has been plotted against μ (Fig. 3). Table IV gives the moments of substituted benzenes.

Fig. 3.

The moments of OCH_3 and OH groups are taken as $\mu \cos 105^\circ$ (*cf.* Evans, Morgan and Watson, *loc. cit.*) since the moments of NO_2 , Cl , Br , CH_3 act in the plane of the benzene ring, while the moments of OCH_3 and OH are inclined to it.

Fig. 3 consists of three sets of curves representing three different series of substituents, *o*, *m* and *p*. The *p*- and *m*-hydroxy substituents

do not fall on the curve due to the low P factors. The unsubstituted ester, however, gives too low a value for the velocity constant and has therefore been excluded. In the present case $\log k_0/Z_0$ does not represent the velocity constant for the unsubstituted ester.

TABLE IV

Substituent	Dipole moment	Effective moment.	Effective moment (meta)	Substituent.	Dipole moment.	Effective inoment.	Effective moment. (meta)
1. NO ₂	-4.24		-2.12	6. CH ₃	0.37		0.18
2. Cl	-1.73		-0.86	7 F	-1.27		-0.78
3. Br	-1.71		-0.86	8. I	-1.36		-0.65
4. CH	-1.40	-0.36	-0.17	9. OC ₂ H ₅	-1.40	-0.36	-0.18
5. OCH ₃	-1.35	-0.34	-0.17	10. NH ₂	1.48	0.39	0.195

Dipole moments of 1-5 and 7-10 taken from Groves and Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 971; 1937, 1782) and that of No. 6 from Groves and Baker (*ibid.*, 1939, 1147).

This observation is quite different from the conclusions drawn by Evans, Morgan and Watson (*loc. cit.*). These workers exclude *o*-substituted compounds and also all resonating groups including the halogens and then proceed to show that the relationship holds irrespective of whether the substituent is in the *p*- or *m*-position. When their observations are studied in detail for the two reactions: (a) acid catalysed prototropy of nuclear substituted acetophenones and (b) alkaline hydrolysis of esters, the agreement between the values of E calculated from the equation and those actually observed, rests with respect to nitro, halogens and methyl groups only in the meta position *i. e.* only four cases.

Fig. 4.

Moreover, while drawing the curves Waston and co-workers have not taken into consideration the effective moments of the *meta*-substituted compounds which will have an effective moment of $\mu \cos 60^\circ$ on the carbonyl carbon atom which is the centre of reaction. The angle 60° is only approximate as this is likely to be changed by the presence of different substituents. If $\log (kVM)$ is plotted against the effective moments of substituted benzenes our results show that a smooth curve results representing all the *m*- and *p*-substituted compounds (Fig. 4). Even *m*- and *p*-hydroxy compounds show little divergence from the curve. In the case of *ortho*-substituted compounds steric hindrance is operative and hence *ortho*-substituted esters are not taken into consideration. A similar relationship is not observed between E , the activation energy, and μ owing to variations in the probability factor, P .

The above discussion can be rendered more definite if the dipole moments of esters of substituted benzoic acids are known. Work in this direction is in progress.

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